

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ONCOLOGY: A LOOK TO THE FUTURE

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Abstract: The article contains a brief overview of the history of development and modern achievements in the field of artificial intelligence, as well as the possibilities of its application in the field of prevention, diagnosis and treatment of oncological diseases. The progress in the field of machine learning related to the development of deep learning technology for neural networks is discussed. Advances in automatic medical image recognition using deep learning, including digital micrographs and radiographs, are reviewed. The possibilities of applying artificial intelligence to the formation of high-risk groups for screening programs are discussed. The problems of introducing artificial intelligence into practical oncology are considered, related to the need for thorough clinical trials of medical technologies using artificial intelligence and the need for large volumes of high-quality data for deep learning of neural networks.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, machine learning, neural networks, automatic recognition, medical images, oncological diseases.

Introduction

Modern achievements in the field of artificial intelligence have shown that computer programs are able to learn and solve poorly formalized tasks, which were previously considered feasible only by the human mind, just as well as a person. In this regard, many large and small research projects are currently being

carried out aimed at exploring the possibilities of the practical use of artificial intelligence in various fields of human activity, including in the field of oncology. Since the beginning of the 21st century, companies that are world leaders in the IT industry have shown significant interest in developments related to the use of artificial intelligence to solve medical problems. For example, at IBM, using the Watson supercomputer based on artificial intelligence algorithms, a program is being created for diagnosing and improving treatment regimens for various diseases, including cancer [1]. Microsoft recently launched the Microsoft Healthcare NExT project, the main focus of which will be the fight against oncological diseases [2]. Google is implementing a number of oncological projects: automatic recognition of tumors in micrographs, collection of genetic and molecular information to compile a detailed map of the body and predict future diseases [3]. On the Kaggle website [4], one of the most popular sites for organizing applied research in the field of artificial intelligence in the form of scientific competitions, you can find many projects related to the practical use of artificial intelligence in oncology in a variety of areas: from automatic recognition of medical images to the classification of genetic mutations and the formation of high-risk groups in order to optimize oncological screening. This paper gives a general idea of artificial intelligence, its history, current state and development prospects. Successful projects demonstrating the possibilities of using artificial intelligence in oncology, as well as problems and prospects for using technologies based on artificial intelligence algorithms in medical practice are discussed.

Artificial intelligence: history, current state, development prospects Artificial intelligence as a branch of informatics, which appeared in the 50s of the XX century and aims to create hardware and software that imitate the abilities of human intelligence, has experienced a number of ups, downs and changes in its short history development paradigms [2]. Almost immediately since the advent of the science of artificial intelligence, two ideas emerged about how artificial intelligence should function. The first idea was to explore the laws of human

thinking and create artificial intelligence as a system that operates data according to these laws. The development of this idea has formed such a direction of artificial intelligence as expert systems. The second idea was to create artificial intelligence in the image and likeness of the human brain. As you know, the human brain consists of a large number of cells - neurons, interconnected and interacting through the reception and transmission of impulses. Therefore, the second major area in artificial intelligence is neural networks. The first significant success in the field of artificial intelligence was a program with the ambitious name "Universal Problem Solver" that appeared in 1959, which could automatically prove theorems and solve problems from the field of mathematical logic [1]. Then, in the second half of the 1950s and early 1960s, the first prototypes of modern neural networks appeared, in particular, the Rosenblatt perceptron, and it began to seem to people that the creation of "smart machines" was within easy reach. However, artificial intelligence could not justify such advances at that time, many announced projects such as the creation of machine translation systems failed, and as a result, the first "winter" of artificial intelligence came.

A large number of training sample records is also necessary for AI to create the necessary classification rules. The more heterogeneous data is loaded into the system at the stage of machine learning, the more accurately these rules will be revealed and the more accurate the result of the AI will be in the end. For example, when processing radiographs and MRI, multilayer neural networks are able to form an idea of the human anatomy and its organs from images. At the same time, computers will not be able to come up with names of organs in their computer classification that are similar to classical medical terminology. Therefore, at first they need a translator from the internal machine dictionary to professional vocabulary. It should be taken into account that due to the nonlinearity, multilayer neural networks do not have an "inverse function", i.e. a computer will generally not be able to explain to a person why he came to this

conclusion. To prepare a motivated judgment, you need a human expert, or, paradoxically, another neural network trained to write correct transcripts and conclusions in natural human language. The supervised learning method is more convenient and preferable in situations where there are accumulated and reliable retrospective initial data: training based on them requires less time and allows you to quickly get a working AI solution. Where the ability to use a database with correlated information and answers to it is not available, self-learning methods based on deep machine learning should be applied - such solutions will not need human supervision.

Artificial intelligence: examples of successful application to solving medical problems.

Currently, many research projects are being implemented related to the application of deep learning technology of neural networks to solving practical problems in the field of medicine and healthcare. Here are some examples of such projects. The detection of diabetic retinopathy from digital photography of the retinal fundus is one of the most successful examples of the use of deep learning technology in medicine [1]. Early screening for diabetic retinopathy is important because early detection and treatment of the disease can prevent visual impairment and blindness in a rapidly growing number of patients with diabetes. Such screening also allows the diagnosis of other diseases of the eye. The growing need for such screening has motivated the creation of a low-cost technology for its implementation. Standards for screening for diabetic retinopathy require at least 80% test sensitivity and 95% specificity. The analysis of digital photography by a medical specialist provides 78% and 96%, respectively, when using photographs from one angle of view, 96% and 89% levels of sensitivity and specificity when analyzing photographs from two angles of view, 92% and 97% when using photographs from three angles of view. Recently, the results of automatic diagnostics using a deep learning algorithm have been demonstrated. The training of the neural network was carried out on a

set of 100,000 photographs from one angle of view. Each image was pre-evaluated by a group of 3–7 ophthalmologists to reach the correct conclusion. The results of testing the algorithm on two sets of images using a single photograph are quite impressive - if high specificity is prioritized (i.e. as few false negatives as possible), then 90.3 / 98.1% and 87.0 / 98.5 are achieved. % sensitivity/specificity. If high sensitivity is prioritized, then 97.5/93.4% and 96.1/93.9% sensitivity/specificity are achieved. Thus, the algorithm, using only one photo, performs better than a person using several photos. Another example of the successful application of neural network technology is the dermatological diagnosis of skin neoplasms [14]. Early diagnosis of skin cancer and melanoma is not an easy task. In the structure of these tumors, only 3–5% is melanoma, which accounts for 75% of deaths from skin neoplasms. Timely diagnosis of melanoma is extremely important, and due to the fact that diagnosis can be performed from a photograph, services have appeared for quite some time that allow people to send a photo of a skin area taken with a regular smartphone to a doctor for analysis. The accuracy of such diagnostics is not very high: the sensitivity is 49%, and the specificity is 98%. The results of automatic diagnostics using an algorithm based on convolutional neural network technology are quite impressive. To train the neural network, a set of 125,000 photographs was used, formed from 18 different electronic storages. It was necessary to perform three-level diagnostics: the first level - it was necessary to determine whether the image contains a benign or malignant tumor or does not have a tumor tissue lesion. At this level, the accuracy was 72.1%, which was better than that achieved by two dermatologists (who achieved 66% and 65.56%, respectively). At the second level, it was required to attribute the disease to one of 9 classes, automatic diagnostics gave 55.4% accuracy, almost the same as that of doctors - 53.3% and 55%, respectively. The results of applying deep learning technology to the problem of automatic recognition and localization of a tumor and its metastases in digital microphotography are also very impressive [15]. This task is very ambitious due

to the fact that even the human intellect copes with this class of tasks with difficulty - it is known, for example, that it takes years and years of practice to become a qualified pathologist capable of diagnosing tumor cells and tissues with high accuracy. Even so, the level of agreement in pathologist diagnoses for some types of breast cancer is only 48%, a similar level - and in the diagnosis of prostate cancer.

The algorithm was trained and tested using a Camelion 16 dataset containing 400 microscopic

Qlarity Imaging's software is used to assist radiologists in the assessment and characterization of breast lesions. Imaging features are synthesized by an artificial intelligence algorithm into a single value, the QI score, which is analyzed relative to a database of reference abnormalities with known ground truth. Image courtesy of Business Wire.

Conclusion

Thus, the currently observed wave of interest in artificial intelligence is explained by the success of deep learning technology for neural networks, which became possible for two reasons: the accumulation of really large amounts of data

in digital form, suitable for training neural network models, and the use of fast neural networks for building and training neural networks. hardware GPUs that allow you to build and train much more complex models than was previously possible. This makes it possible to obtain algorithms that, after training, are able to solve certain classes of poorly formalized problems in various subject areas at a level no worse than the human mind can handle them. Applications of deep learning technology of neural networks to practical problems in the problem area of oncology show the significant potential of artificial intelligence in terms of improving the quality, improving organization and reducing the cost of medical care for cancer patients. Particularly impressive are the advances in the field of automatic recognition of medical images (digital microphotographs, radiographs, etc.). However, there are also a number of objective difficulties. First of all, this is that before being put into practice, these technologies must undergo thorough clinical trials and prove their effectiveness and sustainability. In addition, modern neural network models require large amounts of data for their training, which have the properties of completeness and high quality, which are far from always available even with the modern level of informatization.

References

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